

ABSTRACT

Health insurance is essential in reducing the financial burden of health expenditure for developing countries. It is general knowledge that medical service costs have increased as time goes by. Health insurance makes health care affordable and helps those insured to use health care services appropriately. When people are insured, they certainly feel a sense of security because they know there is no need to shell out money from their pockets when sick. This descriptive-comparative study determines the degree of awareness towards health insurance and the level of health insurance literacy among tertiary students enrolled in a state college in the province of Iloilo. Health Insurance Literacy Questionnaire was used among 301 tertiary students. The findings indicate a high degree of awareness of health insurance and a high level of health insurance literacy among tertiary students. Finally, there is a significant difference in the level of health insurance literacy and the identified variables in this study.

Keywords: *Health Insurance, Literacy, Tertiary Students, descriptive-comparative design, Philippines.*

INTRODUCTION

Health insurance is essential in reducing the financial burden of health expenditure for developing countries (Zhang et al., 2010). Health insurance companies have been in the online market for many years, serving all of us in the face of growing medical costs (Connell, 2006). It is general knowledge that medical service costs have increased as time goes by. At this point, our savings have been depleted due to the high hospital bills. Health insurance makes health care affordable and helps those insured to use health care services appropriately (Bernstein et al., 2010). When people are insured, they certainly feel a sense of security because they know that there is no need to shell out money from their pockets when they are sick (Barber, 2021).

Health insurance is an insurance product that covers an insured individual's medical and surgical expenses (Song et al., 2014). It reimburses the costs incurred due to illness (Kankeu, 2013). As young students nowadays see health insurance as nothing but less or no value since most of their priorities are things that can make them happy or bring comfort to their lives (Evans & Stoddart, 2017). Aside from wanting to land a better job once they graduate, they also want to enjoy traveling to as many places as possible. When it comes to their health, students or young people are less likely to care (Younes et al., 2015). They usually believe they are less likely to be hospitalized or get sick (Hope et al., 2017). They are prone to these because of their lifestyle, particularly the type of food they eat daily. They are skeptical about the consequences on their bodies. The right health insurance plan that their parents can provide will benefit them and their parents, who will carry all of the burdens of the high cost of medical treatments and hospitalization when they get sick. The benefits of health insurance should be introduced thoroughly to these young people, including a basic understanding of the financial and medical costs so that they can understand it very well and make it one of their top priorities (Drechsler & Jütting, 2005). They should be taught about the benefits of health insurance, the importance of having health insurance, and the person's right to health insurance (Sonnino, 2016).

United Health Care Student Resources (2016) states that health and wellness are critical to academic success. Insured students stay healthier by utilizing recommended preventive care services that help avoid health issues and possibly detect health issues that need attention. The primary purpose of student health insurance is to keep students healthy and in school so they can graduate and realize their life and career goals (Salazar et al., 2016).

There are various benefits to having health insurance (Sommers et al., 2017). It provides financial protection for individuals and their families like home or car insurance does. Even if a person is in good health, we will never know when an accident or an illness will occur. A person's most valuable asset is their health. A good health insurance plan can help protect policyholders and their family's health and financial future for a lifetime. It makes sense to get covered now that there are new ways to obtain affordable health insurance.

Health insurance has become imperative in our lives (Hoofman, 2002). Having health insurance has many benefits (Gaba, 2004). One of the most benefits is financial security. A health insurance policy is intended to provide individuals and their families with the resources to pay for unexpected medical care and hospitalization (Atake, 2020). It is essential to be prepared all the time. Health insurance ensures that our medical needs will be covered in case we need it. Avoid going into

deep debt or bankruptcy. Health insurance is fundamental to living a safe and healthy life (Bircher & Kuruvilla, 2014).

Health insurance is essential in our lives because it protects us from the unexpected and covers the cost of living (Castillo et al., 2011). One may not realize the value of health insurance while they are still young and healthy, but trust the experts; when we get older and start to feel uneasy because of a sickness, we will realize how important it is to have health insurance. Health insurance helps people when they are sick and helps them avoid getting sick because of their annual check-ups or vaccinations, which are also covered by their health insurance plan. The amount of money taken out of one's pocket when hospitalized without health insurance is much more significant than the amount one will pay for the right health insurance plan (Kastor & Mohanty, 2018). It is always good to be prepared rather than sorry later. It is also a method of ensuring our health against illness. Remember that our health is the most valuable asset. A good health insurance plan will protect our family and us from financial loss and secure our financial future for a lifetime (Ganz, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study utilized a quantitative descriptive-comparative research design. This paper employed quantitative descriptive research to measure the students' degree of awareness of health insurance and their health insurance literacy level. The descriptive-comparative research was used to measure the difference in students' health insurance literacy level according to their demographics using standardized and adopted tests to extract data appropriately.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study involved 301 out of 1,266 tertiary students enrolled in a state college in the province of Iloilo for the academic year 2022-2023. The number of respondents was determined using stratified random sampling. The sample size was computed using the Raosoft calculator. The fishbowl method was utilized to establish randomization in selecting and including respondents.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher wrote a letter to the office of the SUC President of a state college in the province of Iloilo, asking for permission to conduct the study in their prestigious educational institution with their tertiary students as respondents of the study. Informed consent was secured from the respondents by including an informed consent form in the survey questionnaire to secure that participation in the study is voluntary. After securing the permits from key state college officials, the researcher scheduled a specific date for the survey's actual administration. The researcher administered the questionnaire. After gathering the data, the researcher encoded the raw data and sent the excel file to the statistician for analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis Procedure. The researcher used frequency count to determine the respondents' profiles when grouped according to sex, year level, and department. The quantitative data from the health insurance literacy questionnaire was analyzed to determine the significant difference between the student's literacy level and their demographics. The main problem of the study employed the descriptive analysis, explicitly using the mean to determine the degree of awareness towards health insurance and the level of health insurance literacy among tertiary students when they are taken as a whole and when they are grouped according to the identified variables. For the inferential problems, comparative analysis, specifically with the independent sample t-test, was used to determine the difference in the students' health insurance literacy level when they were grouped according to their sex. At the same time, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the difference in students' health insurance literacy level when they were classified according to their year level and department.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographics of the students enrolled for the first semester of the academic year 2022-2023 as the respondents of this study. The data shows that 301 students comprise the total population of the respondents. When grouped according to sex, female students constitute 48% of the total population, and the remaining 52% are male students. Regarding the year level, the respondents are equally distributed to 25% for each year level. Students enrolled in the College of Management makeup 34% of the total population; for the remaining percentage, the College of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences and College of Education got 33% each, respectively.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Variables	N	%
TOTAL	301	100
Sex	125	42
Male	176	58
Female		
Year Level		
First-year	76	25
Second year	75	25
Third year	75	25
Fourth-year	75	25
Department		
CM	101	34
COED	100	33
CFAS	100	33

Degree of Awareness towards Health Insurance among students

Table 2 shows the degree of awareness towards health insurance among students at Iloilo State College of Fisheries. As a whole ($M=3.64$, $SD=0.50$), students' degree of awareness towards health insurance is high. When students are grouped according to sex, the degree of awareness towards health insurance among students is both high, with female students garnering a mean score of 3.60 ($SD=0.51$) and male students scoring 3.68 ($SD=0.53$). Considering the year level of the students, third-year ($M=3.82$, $SD=0.51$) students got the highest mean score, followed by the fourth-year ($M=3.77$, $SD=0.49$) students, next is the second-year ($M=3.53$, $SD=0.46$) and lastly, the first year students got a mean score of 3.42 ($SD=0.51$); regardless of their year level, students got a high mean score. With regards to their department, the students from the College of Management ($M=3.76$, $SD=0.47$) got the highest mean score, followed by the College of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences ($M=3.63$, $SD=0.57$) and College of Education ($M=3.51$, $SD=0.49$).

When taken as a whole, students enrolled in Iloilo State College of Fisheries got a mean score of 3.64 ($SD=0.50$), meaning they have a high degree of awareness towards health insurance. A high degree of awareness towards health insurance is interpreted as a high degree of consciousness about the sense of security that an individual is ensured to have medical benefits that may help reduce medical expenses when hospitalized. These data may imply that students are responsible for securing health insurance, especially now that they are experiencing the new normal of healthcare systems.

When students are grouped according to sex, both sexes garnered a mean score that is interpreted as high. The data may imply that regardless of sex, an individual may perceive health insurance as essential amidst the diversity and challenges these students face. The results of the current study are similar to the findings of Makaula et al. (2012), where they found that males and females have the same degree of perception towards health insurance and see the vital role it plays in cost-effective practices.

Considering the students' year level, it is noted that all respondents from various year levels scored high. The data means that regardless of the student's year level, they are highly aware of the importance of securing a health insurance policy.

Lastly, when grouped according to the department, students have a high degree of awareness towards health insurance regardless of their college department. It signifies that students from the College of Management, College of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences, and College of Education have perceived the essential role of health insurance in securing a lower amount or bill when they need to be hospitalized and require essential medical services.

Table 2. Degree of Awareness towards Health Insurance among students

Variables	M	SD	Interpretation
TOTAL	3.64	0.50	High
Sex			
Male	3.68	0.53	High
Female	3.60	0.51	High
Year Level			
First-year	3.42	0.51	High
Second year	3.53	0.46	High
Third year	3.82	0.51	High
Fourth-year	3.77	0.49	High
Department			
CM	3.76	0.47	High
COED	3.51	0.49	High
CFAS	3.63	0.57	High

Health Insurance Services as perceived by the students

Table 3 shows the results for the health insurance services needed or to be included in a health insurance policy. The top four services that should be included in health insurance services are as follow ambulance charges (M=4.18, SD=0.96), daily hospitalization allowance (M=3.70, SD=0.90), permanent total disability (M=3.63, SD=0.84), and consultation fees (M=3.62, SD=1.09). In continuation, accidental death and disablement (M=3.57, SD=0.90) ranked fifth, followed by daily hospitalization (M=3.51, SD=0.87), accident due to insect bite (M=3.49, SD=0.96), and accidental medical reimbursement (M=3.34, SD=0.89).

Table 3. Health Insurance Services as perceived by the students

Services	M	SD	Interpretation
Ambulance charges	4.18	0.96	High
Consultation fees	3.62	1.09	High
Accidental death & disablement	3.57	0.90	High
Permanent total disability	3.63	0.84	High
Daily hospitalization	3.51	0.87	High
Accident due to insect bite (Dengue)	3.49	0.96	High
Accidental medical reimbursement	3.34	0.89	High
Daily hospitalization allowance	3.70	0.90	High

Health Insurance Literacy Level of students

Table 4 presents students' health insurance literacy level at Iloilo State College of Fisheries. When taken as a whole (M=3.28, SD=0.54), the results show that students have a high level of health insurance literacy. When they are grouped according to sex, female students got a mean score of 3.21 (SD=0.50), and male students scored 3.37 (0.61), both interpreted as high literacy levels towards health insurance. Considering the year level of the students, fourth-year students got the highest mean score of 3.52 (SD=0.65), followed by the third-year students (M=3.34, SD=0.54), next is the first-year students with a score of 3.29 (SD=0.32), and lastly, the second year students got the lowest mean score of 2.95 (SD=0.50). With regards to the department as a variable, students from the College of Education got a mean score of 3.19 (SD=0.34), on other hand, students from the College of Management got a score of 3.28 (SD=0.37), and lastly, the students from the College of Fisheries and Aquatic Science got a mean score of 3.36 (SD=0.81).

When taken as a whole, student respondents got a mean score of 3.28 (SD=0.54), which is verbally interpreted as a high level of health insurance literacy. Students from a state college are highly aware and literate about the importance of having health insurance. This further signifies that students are conscious of the importance of acquiring health insurance despite their young age. When given a chance, they may subscribe to a health insurance policy if they have the appropriate and adequate resources to finance their needs.

Across year level, students in first, third, and fourth years got a high level of health insurance literacy, among others; on the other hand, the second-year students got an average level of health insurance literacy. The data may imply that students from the first year, third, and fourth years have a high level of literacy that may affect their decision to avail of health insurance later in life when they can do so. At the same time, second-year students got an average level of literacy, which can also give them doubts about availing of health insurance policies later in life, even if they have the capacity and financial stability.

When students are grouped according to the department, students from the College of Management and College of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences get a high level of health insurance literacy. The data may imply that the student's perception of health insurance may be affected by various backgrounds and orientations. The students from the College of Education got an average mean score, which signifies that students may be skeptical about health insurance but somehow has a part in them that they want to avail if allowed to avail health insurance.

This study's results differ from McCormack et al. (2009), in which they found that older adults have a low to moderate level of health insurance literacy. They have also concluded that those with lower levels of health insurance literacy are also older adults with lower education and income.

Table 4. Health Insurance Literacy Level of students

Variables	M	SD	Interpretation
TOTAL	3.28	0.54	High
Sex			
Male	3.37	0.61	High
Female	3.21	0.50	High
Year Level			
First-year	3.29	0.32	High
Second year	2.95	0.50	Average
Third year	3.34	0.54	High
Fourth-year	3.52	0.65	High
Department			
CM	3.28	0.37	High
COED	3.19	0.34	Average
CFAS	3.36	0.81	High

The difference in the Health Insurance Literacy Level of students

Table 5 shows the difference in the level of health insurance literacy among the students enrolled in a state college in the province of Iloilo. Considering sex as a variable, male students (M=3.37, SD=0.61) scored better than female students (M=3.21, SD=0.50). An Independent sample t-test was used to analyze the difference between male and female students. The difference (t=2.51) was significant (p=0.000) among male and female students. The sex as a variable in this study is considered valuable because it proved that there is a difference in the results when comparing the two sexes.

The results of this study are different from the findings of the previous study by Bartholomae et al. (2016), where they stated that male respondents scored lower than their female counterparts. This finding may signify that females are more conscious of their health compared to males, but in the case of students in a state college, males are more conscious about their health compared to female students.

Table 5. Differences in the Health Insurance Literacy Level of students when grouped according to sex

Health Insurance Literacy	Sex		t	df	p-value
	Male	Female			
	3.37	3.21	2.51	299	0.000

Table 6 shows the difference in the department and year level as variables. When grouped according to year level, students in their fourth year scored the highest compared to those in the lower years. One-way Analysis of Variance is used to treat the data and find out the difference in the level of health insurance literacy among college students. The difference ($F=16.02$) was significant ($p=0.000$) between fourth-year, third-year, second-year, and first-year students. Year level is considered a valuable variable in this study because of the difference among year levels.

When grouped according to the department, the difference ($F=2.44$) was insignificant ($p=0.089$) between the College of Management, Education and the College of Fisheries and Aquatic Science. This implies that department is the only variable with no significant difference among the respondents of this study.

Table 6. Differences in the Health Insurance Literacy Level of students when grouped according to year level and department

Variables	Mean Scores				F	p-value
	First-year	Second year	Third year	Fourth-year		
Year Level	3.29	2.95	3.34	3.52	16.02	0.000
Department	CM	COED	CFAS		2.44	0.089
	3.28	3.19	3.36			

CONCLUSION

The degree of awareness of students enrolled in a state college in the province of Iloilo for the academic year 2022-2023 was high. College students, in general, consider health insurance a necessity. These further imply that college students are conscious of the vital role of health insurance if they ever get sick in the future, especially in the new normal of the healthcare system due to the global pandemic that we have recently experienced.

The essential services perceived by the students needing a health insurance policy are ambulatory charges, daily hospitalization allowance, permanent total disability, and consultation fees. These are the necessary services that must be considered by health insurance companies when they craft their policies.

In general, the college student's level of health insurance literacy is high; only the second-year students and students from the College of Education got an average literacy level. These signify that, in general, students appreciate the importance of being enrolled in a health insurance policy that may help lessen the medical bills and expenses if any unfortunate events happen.

Finally, a significant difference in health insurance literacy among college students was established. Furthermore, there was a significant difference in the student's level of health insurance literacy when sex and year level was considered; the department was the only variable that was found to be insignificant. Therefore, college students, regardless of their sex and year level, have a great sense of responsibility and accountability toward their health.

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